

RI-VIS D2.1 Data Set

Project title	RI-VIS
Grant Agreement No.	824063
Deliverable number	2.1
Deliverable title	Data set
Lead beneficiary	ECRIN
Contributing beneficiaries	EMPHASIS
Author(s)	Serena Battaglia, Sven Fahrner
Type	Report
Work package No.	2
Work package title	Mapping and enabling new partnerships
Dissemination level	Public
Due date (in months)	12
Delivery date (actual)	06/02/20
Description of deliverable	Information on services targeting new partners

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
<i>Detailed report on the deliverable</i>	2
Background/Introduction	2
Description of work	3
Conclusion/Next steps	4
References	5

Executive Summary

The objectives of this work package are to: ‘map’ the RIs and their services, and to learn from existing collaboration between European RIs and third-country partners as well as with industry partners; to identify gaps in terms of communication; and to determine opportunities for new cooperation and to identify the conditions to develop such cooperation.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

European and global research infrastructures (RIs) provide facilities and resources to support excellence and innovation, delivering socio-economic value by raising skills, advancing knowledge and technology and its exploitation, and driving new developments. RIs already interact closely with their specialist communities, but RI sustainability in the long term requires engagement with civil society and other stakeholders. An understanding of the significance and the socioeconomic benefits of the services delivered by RIs is critical to garner financial and strategic support from diverse stakeholders.

Most of the European RIs participating in RI-VIS cover the whole spectrum of biological and medical research: discovery and development of health challenges, from marine biology to structural biology, chemical libraries, and animal models, as well as human biobanks, and translational and clinical research. In addition partners from environmental and social sciences can ensure the development of cross-cutting and general services as well as the outreach to a larger audience than life science research communities

New technologies are currently transforming several areas of research. The RIs are at the heart of this revolution; they provide scientific communities with access to specialised research services and facilities to tackle the grand health and demographic challenges in Europe.

As research instruments accessible to scientific communities, RIs focus on technological and methodological expertise and services, and enable researchers to concentrate on the scientific content. The objective of RI-VIS is to increase the visibility of European RIs to broader scientific communities, and industry and strategic partners in third countries. To this end, task 2.1 aims to develop and establish a comprehensive dataset of existing and forthcoming RI services based on previous activities such as RISCAPE [1], MERIL [2] and CatRIS [3].

Description of work

The MERIL project performed a mapping of the European Research Infrastructures across scientific disciplines (<https://portal.meril.eu>). As RI-VIS is focused on visibility and partnership outside Europe the MERIL portal was not necessarily useful for the present deliverable; nevertheless it can provide a source of information to establish collaboration with international RIs interested in a particular field in Europe.

The RISCAGE project performed a landscape analysis of RIs beyond Europe. The analysis identified the most relevant initiatives in each scientific area, as well as relevant initiatives related to organisation/governance and services.

The full RISCAGE report, including methodology and the list of the identified international RIs, is available [here](https://riscape.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/RISCAGE_consolidated_301219.pdf) [4]: https://riscape.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/RISCAGE_consolidated_301219.pdf; the main findings are summarised below.

To fulfil RI-VIS' objectives, WP2 focuses on select topics that are relevant to facilitate international partnerships:

i) Development of new collaborations

Communication is a key element in establishing new contacts for future partnerships. The organisations identified by RISCAGE are similar to European RIs, and, as such, are familiar with the technical jargon and governance of EU RIs. Despite this familiarity among like-minded (non-European) organisations, it is essential to develop a common language and key messages to increase visibility among users and policy makers (both in Europe and beyond). To that end, under the responsibility of WP5, a communication toolkit is under preparation, to better communicate about RIs and their missions, as well as to help identify the best engagement strategies.

ii) User accessibility

Excellence and feasibility of a research project are the main criteria to access services provided by RIs. All RIs offer services, which can range from simple consultation (advice) or access to experts, to access to data and biological samples, use of data analysis tools, access to facilities (e.g. highly specialised microscopes) with support from technicians, and much more. In the context of the CORBEL project [5], a collaborative project from the biomedical cluster of research infrastructures, a Catalogue of Services (<https://www.corbel-project.eu/services.html>) was developed to list the main services provided by all the biomedical EU RIs at a glance, with the objective of helping researchers to have an understanding of the services offered, and to identify the most relevant services for their research projects. This represents quite a unique model, as the RIs in the other world regions are not organised in 'clusters' and do not offer a 'brokerage service' to help researchers identify the optimal solution for their research question. The regional workshops organised by RI-VIS would be the opportunity to present the CORBEL model, which, in the future, could be expanded beyond Europe. A catalogue of similar and specific services offered by international RIs could be developed. Indeed, throughout the RISCAGE report, it is shown that most of the RIs plan to develop new facilities and services or to adapt their existing services to users' needs. The main proposed developments are investment in emerging technologies; increase in capacity or incorporation of existing expert facilities within the infrastructures; and upgrading of facilities and instruments. To

that end, a collaboration with the ongoing CatRIS project, which is developing a portal listing all the services provided by the European RIs, could be established.

iii) *Collaborative and innovative actions*

Almost 75% of the international RIs analysed in RISCAPE have scientific collaborations or exchanges with European organisations (individual institutes or universities), often in the context of global networks. However, less than a half have already established or signed a formal collaboration agreement with a European RI in the corresponding scientific field. In addition, in rare cases, European RIs are not known outside Europe. This can be explained either by the relatively recent development of some European RIs, or by the fact that some RIs have long-lasting scientific partnerships, and therefore do not seek new partners outside of Europe. This represents a major challenge for international visibility. The regional workshops as well as the engagement strategies planned in RI-VIS should help to overcome these obstacles.

iv) *Funding opportunities*

As in Europe, the majority of international RIs are directly funded by the government or governmental agencies. This governmental funding can be the unique source of funding (65%) or can be combined with other sources, either public or private, including user fees. The funding model can represent a major obstacle in international partnerships and will be discussed during the regional workshops.

v) *Training opportunities*

Training is often offered by all RIs, and targets both facility end-users and a broader audience. It can represent an opportunity to establish international partnerships via tools that are relatively easy to implement (i.e. webinars). In addition, as part of the RI-VIS engagement strategy, staff-visits and training modules will also be offered.

Ultimately, based on the identified RIs, WP2 and WP3 have selected potential local contacts to establish a group of regional 'champions' to support the organisation of the three workshops in the regions selected for international engagement (see Milestone MS4).

Conclusion/Next steps

Based on the RISCAPE findings, the RI-VIS consortium has identified several key aspects to be addressed for a successful partnership strategy. The solutions suggested will be presented and discussed during the regional workshops and a report summarising the outcomes will be prepared after each workshop.

References

- [1] RISCAPE – European Research Infrastructures in the International landscape (H2020 GA 730974) <https://riscap.eu/>
- [2] MERIL – Mapping of the European Research Infrastructures Landscape (H2020 GA 654296)
- [3] CatRIS – Catalogue of Research Infrastructure Services (H2020 GA 824173)
- [4] Asmi, Ari, Ryan, Lorna, Salmon, Emmanuel, Kubiak, Christine, Battaglia, Serena, Förster, Miriam, ... Sundet, Jostein. (2019, December 30). International Research Infrastructure Landscape 2019 (Version 1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3539254>
- [5] CORBEL – Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science Services (H2020 GA 654248)